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THE IMPACT OF HUMAN RESOURCE INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN ROMANIAN RECRUITMENT COMPANIES

Abstract: This article explores the significant influence of Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS) on the recruitment practices within Romanian companies. Specifically, the article examines how automating various HR processes—both routine and non-routine—affects HR operations, contributes to time and cost savings, enhances information flow, improves decision-making, and aligns HR strategically with employees' perceptions. By focusing on the methodology and results, we provide a comprehensive overview of the tools and strategies employed by Romanian firms, highlighting the transformation from

traditional to modern recruitment methods, and the resulting efficiencies and challenges.

Keywords: Human Resource Information Systems, Digitalization of HR, Information Systems

1. Introduction

For a long time, the HR department was primarily seen as an administrative tool focused on hiring and maintaining employee records. Due to the complexity of information processed by HR and its lack of strategic consideration, it was the last organizational function to receive IT support. Initially, HR was viewed as a cost to be minimized, but over the past three decades, the implementation of Human Resources Information Systems (HRIS) has transformed HR from a purely administrative role to a strategic asset.

The gradual automation of HR functions began in the 1970s with the introduction of company-wide ERP systems that included HR modules. In the late 1980s, PeopleSoft introduced the first HR-centered client-server system. By the late 1990s, employee self-service tools became common, allowing employees to update their information and access HR-related services online.

With the advent of the 21st century, HRIS solutions expanded to include online recruitment tools, time and attendance recording, skill tracking, predictive analytics, training modules, performance appraisal, and career management systems. These systems have made HR processes more efficient, reliable, and strategically valuable.

HRIS now encompasses various HR functions such as recruitment, time and attendance, absence management, employee motivation, performance evaluation, training and development, career management, and payroll. These functions are categorized into operational, functional/relational, and strategic levels, highlighting HR's role as a business partner in achieving organizational goals.

2. HRIS worldwide

HRIS¹ are essential tools for managing HR functions such as maintenance, recruitment, usage, and performance evaluation. HRIS integrates software, hardware, support functions, and policies into an automated process that supports both strategic and operational HR activities. These systems maintain a database of employee information, job performance, and positions, facilitating transaction processing, reporting, and tracking (Figure 1).

¹ Bondarouk, T. V. (2011). Theoretical approaches to e-HRM implementations. In T. Bondarouk, H. Ruel, & J. C. Looise (Eds.), *Electronic HRM in theory and practice*, Advanced Series in Management, Vol 24.

Figure 1 – Human Resources Information Systems

Source: adaptation after <https://www.thehumancapitalhub.com/articles/what-is-human-resources-information-systems>

HRIS provides analytical tools that help managers set objectives and assess HR procedures¹. They align HR functions with long-term organizational goals and support the reengineering of HR processes to enhance speed, effectiveness, and cost efficiency. This integration allows HR professionals to adapt to organizational changes and foster an innovative, knowledge-based work environment.

Studies indicate that HRIS contributes to organizational competitiveness by reducing costs and improving productivity, quality, and profitability. However, there is a lack of standardization in software integration, partly due to gaps in employee training and IT knowledge. Increasing education and training in IT for HR staff is crucial to fully leverage these systems.

HRIS are also beneficial² in job placement and promotion planning, enhancing e-recruiting processes by efficiently organizing employee data. This leads to significant time and cost savings and necessitates the redesign and integration of HR systems. Self-service HRIS improves accuracy, reduce the HR-to-staff ratio, save time, and empower employees. Overall, HRIS³ are vital for improving organizational effectiveness and supporting modern HR practices.

3. HR and HRIS in Romania

¹ CedarCrestone (2011). Going global with HR technologies: One organizational model consistently outperforms! [Electronic version].

² Kavanagh, M. J., Johnson R. D., eds. Human resource information systems: Basics, applications, and future directions. Sage Publications, 2017.

³ Ramli, M., Sarinah, L., Nugraha, R. N., & Januarty, D. F. (2024). Human Resource Management at Mie Gacoan Jatiasih. West Science Social and Humanities Studies, 2(04), 683-691.

According to experts¹, the evolution of Human Resources Management (HRM) in Romanian organizations has gone through several phases, each characterized by different priorities and approaches:

Phase 1: Pro-Management - This initial phase prioritized legal aspects and personnel administration.

Phase 2: Pre-Management - The focus shifted to quantitative activities and cost minimization in personnel administration.

Phase 3: Authentic Human Resources Management - Emphasis moved to qualitative aspects such as recruitment, selection, promotion, communication processes, professional ethics, and performance-based compensation.

In the first phase, HR activities were primarily legal and administrative². The second phase saw a transition towards cost efficiency and the perception of personnel as a cost to be minimized. The third phase marked a significant shift, valuing qualitative aspects of HR³, leading to more sophisticated personnel management practices.

The current phase, Authentic Human Resources Management, views human capital as a resource to be optimized. This phase emphasizes values, ethical practices, and result-based rewards, highlighting the evolution of HR activities and their integration into organizational values.

Despite these developments, the progression of HRM in Romania⁴ has not been extensively documented. This research aims to fill that gap by exploring the transition to HRIS. It will specifically focus on modern recruitment processes within Romanian companies, illustrating the shift from traditional personnel data administration to advanced HR practices using software and applications.

3. Research methodology

This study aims to investigate the modern recruiting methods used by Romanian companies, examining whether traditional methods are still employed and how contemporary tools are utilized to find ideal candidates. It also seeks to identify similarities in recruitment strategies across different industries within Romania.

The research explores the significant evolution in recruitment practices during Romania's recent democratic period, emphasizing the necessity for companies to adopt new information management methods to remain competitive. While small companies might not require customized HR information systems due to their limited data and workforce, medium to large companies benefit greatly from such systems to manage and analyze extensive data efficiently.

¹ Panaite N., Abrudan M. M., Bedrule – Grigoruță M. V., Manolescu I. T., Neșțian A. Ș., Petrișor I., Prodan A., Osoian C., Vărzaru M., Zaharie M. (2015). *Managementul Resurselor Umane în Organizațiile din România*. Editura Expert

² Berceanu, I.B., Nicolescu, C.E., 2024. Collaborative Public Administration—A Dimension of Sustainable Development: Exploratory Study on Local Authorities in Romania. *Administrative Sciences*, 14(2), p.30.

³ Kavanagh, M. J., Johnson R. D., eds. *Human resource information systems: Basics, applications, and future directions*. Sage Publications, 2017.

⁴ Cojocariu, L.L., Copăcean, L., Ursu, A., Sărățeanu, V., Popescu, C.A., Horablaga, M.N., Bordean, D.M., Horablaga, A., Bostan, C., 2024. Assessment of the Impact of Population Reduction on Grasslands with a New “Tool”: A Case Study on the “Mountainous Banat” Area of Romania. *Land*, 13(2), p.134.

Additionally, the study aims to assist managers in assessing the need for and extent of HRIS implementation and identifying potential issues in their usage. For the purposes of this research, "Romanian companies" include any organization with local Romanian management, regardless of whether they are multinationals, as they operate within and adapt to the Romanian market.

3.1. Research Questions and Objectives

This section outlines the research questions and the corresponding objectives this study seeks to address:

a) What modern and traditional recruitment methods do Romanian companies use?

This question investigates whether companies, despite the availability of modern technology, continue to use traditional recruitment methods and the reasons for their persistence. Additionally, it aims to identify the modern techniques employed in recruitment processes, evaluating the efficacy of these contemporary methods.

b) Are there any similarities in recruitment methods among companies operating in different industries?

This question explores whether companies in various industries utilize similar recruitment channels. It seeks to identify both modern and traditional channels used across different sectors to determine any commonalities in their recruitment strategies.

c) Do recruiters personally use traditional methods for recruiting potential candidates?

The purpose here is to examine whether recruiters still find traditional recruitment methods useful and to what extent these methods are personally employed in the recruitment process.

d) Do companies use recruitment metrics, and do they have software to analyze these metrics?

This question aims to determine if companies have implemented recruitment metrics and whether they use software to analyze these metrics. It also seeks to uncover any similarities in the metrics used by different companies.

e) What are the advantages and disadvantages of using software to store and analyze recruitment metrics data?

This question assesses the perceived benefits and drawbacks of using software for recruitment metrics from the recruiters' perspective. It aims to identify any areas where the software may fall short compared to traditional methods.

The objective of the above questions is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current recruitment practices in Romanian companies, their reliance on both modern and traditional methods, and the role of technology in enhancing recruitment efficiency. This study also aims to inform managers about

the potential need for HRIS implementation and highlight any challenges faced in its usage.

3.2 Research Design

This thesis employs an exploratory research design, focusing on qualitative data collection due to the limited existing research on this topic in Romania. The qualitative approach is chosen because the scarcity of recruiters in company HR departments makes it challenging to conduct descriptive research with quantitative data.

Qualitative research involves gathering non-numerical data to gain an in-depth understanding of phenomena within a specific context. This approach emphasizes understanding the reasons behind occurrences rather than just identifying what is happening. The goals of qualitative research can vary based on the disciplinary background, reflecting different objectives and purposes depending on the field of study. This research aims to uncover why recruiters and companies use both modern and traditional recruitment methods, if they continue to use them.

To collect the necessary qualitative data, the primary instrument will be an interview questionnaire. This method is selected because it is more feasible to find willing participants to complete an interview questionnaire compared to arranging face-to-face interviews. It is also less time-consuming for respondents and easier to schedule. The interview questionnaire will cover several topics, including the most commonly used modern recruitment tools, the continued use of traditional methods, and the reasons behind the preference for modern tools over older methods.

3.3 The Sample

The target sample for this research comprises recruiters from the Human Resources departments of two Romanian companies operating in different industries. The objective is to identify similarities and differences in their recruitment methods and tools, including the use of traditional and modern recruitment techniques. To ensure fairness, companies with the same number of recruiters will be selected to minimize discrepancies in the results.

The chosen companies are two multinationals based in Iasi, referred to as Company A and Company B for confidentiality. Company A operates in the automotive industry and has had a local branch in Iasi for 10 years, employing approximately 2,400 people. Company B, which operates in the Digital Video Recording industry, has been present in the local market for 4 years and employs 120 people. Both companies have four recruiters in their HR departments, making them suitable for a comparative study.

These multinationals are considered Romanian companies because they have local Romanian management, adhere to Romanian laws, and operate within the Romanian market. Their workforce primarily consists of Romanian employees, and they adapt to local cultural and market trends. The internal environment of these companies is influenced by Romanian cultural values and needs, further justifying their classification as Romanian companies.

Given the small number of recruiters, data will be analyzed using a matrix. Relevant questions from the interview-questionnaire will be selected, and the primary criterion for analysis will be the recruiters' years of experience. The data will be examined based on the frequency of responses to identify commonalities and unique differences.

The proposed timeframe for applying, collecting, and analyzing the data is 2 to 3 months. This extended period accounts for the initial difficulty in establishing connections with the HR departments, as it coincided with a busy recruitment season. Additionally, assistance from industry connections was sought to facilitate the research process.

4. Conclusion and Future Research

This study reveals that organizations are increasingly adopting modern recruitment methods such as posting job opportunities on social media and job platforms, headhunting on social media, administering online technical and psychological assessments, utilizing internal acquisition software, and analyzing recruiting metrics with specialized software. These modern tools are preferred by most recruiters for their convenience, efficiency, and ability to reach a larger pool of candidates, thus enabling better selection and faster targeting.

However, one respondent indicated a continued reliance on traditional methods, contingent on the position and candidate type. Unique traditional methods identified include the use of recruitment agencies by the Digital Video Recording industry and recruitment events by the Automotive industry. Both companies also employ a referral and bonus system as a common traditional recruitment method.

Recruitment metrics used by these companies are generally advantageous, offering qualitative reports, trend identification, problem-solving insights, period comparisons, and reduced manual work. The primary drawbacks are double data entry, extra data, and limited usefulness of some data, used infrequently.

The findings indicate a clear preference for digital recruitment methods in the Romanian market, with traditional methods still in use depending on industry and job type. For small companies, custom software and online assessments may be unnecessary due to their limited employee numbers and higher relative costs. Free online tools such as Google Docs, Sheets, Forms, Prezi, Google Hangouts, Gmail, Skype, LinkedIn, and Facebook can be more practical. Small companies can manage and supervise their employees more easily compared to larger organizations.

Medium to large companies, however, should consider integrating custom software and digital tools to enhance efficiency, reduce redundancy, and save time, thereby increasing overall output. This should be viewed as a long-term investment with future rewards.

This research can benefit foreign organizations entering the Romanian market by providing insights into local recruitment practices, reducing their analysis and benchmarking costs, and aiding faster adaptation to current trends. Multinational companies may already employ similar recruitment methods, including internal acquisition software and various assessments and metrics.

For medium to large Romanian companies, the findings offer new methods and insights into targeting candidates and improving recruitment processes. Additionally, HR departments of existing Romanian companies can use this research for benchmarking and operational improvements.

Future research could explore employees' perceptions of HRIS within their companies. Investigations could focus on whether HRIS meets employee expectations, its impact on daily HR processes, integration into organizational culture, time savings, decision-making influence, and information dissemination efficiency.

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